

A review of Graph Neural Networks for Electroencephalography data analysis

Manuel Graña^{*}, Igone Morais-Quilez

Computational Intelligence Group, CCIA dept., University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), San Sebastian, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Graph Neural Networks
Electroencephalography
EEG
Graph Convolutional Networks
Neural Networks

ABSTRACT

Electroencephalography (EEG) sensors are flexible and non-invasive sensing devices for the measurement of electrical brain activity which is extensively used in some areas of clinical practice and psychological/psychiatric research, such as epilepsy, sleep, emotion, and brain computer interfaces. Although EEG sensor do not provide actual brain localizations of the activity sources, they allow to study brain functional connectivity. In this paper we review current application of a specific family of computational methods, the Graph Neural Networks (GNN) to the analysis of EEG data. GNNs appear to be well suited to EEG data modeling as they deal with signals whose domain is defined by a graph instead of a regular lattice in Euclidean space. Readings of EEG electrodes fall in this category, hence the increasing research activity on the application of GNNs to EEG data.

1. Introduction

In short, Graph Neural Networks (GNN) are a family of neural network architectures that deal with signals whose domain is defined by a graph structure instead of a lattice embedded in an Euclidean space. A recent review [1] proposes a new taxonomy into four categories: recurrent GNNs, convolutional GNNs, graph auto-encoders, and spatial-temporal GNNs. Most of the works reviewed in this paper fall in the category of convolutional GNNs (GCN), so we will be using these acronyms indistinctly. The interest of the application of GNNs to Electroencephalography (EEG) data comes from the early works on the study of the brain using graph theoretical analysis in order to understand the impact of the complex networks involved in its function [2].

The use of EEG data has a long tradition in the study of the brain function for psychological and clinical purposes. It provides a non-invasive diagnostic tool for the study of the bioelectrical functional alterations of the brain. EEG measurements directly reflect the operation of synapses in real-time [3]. Compared with metabolic signal detection by fMRI or PET, EEG offers several additional attractive features: non-invasiveness, high time-resolution, wide availability, low cost, and direct access to neuronal signaling for biomarker identification in psychiatric diseases and dementias [4]. However, EEG has been also used for marketing and directed advertisement, such as in the study of reactions to TV commercials [5].

The content of the paper is as follows: Section 2 gives a rather general panorama of the application of Machine Learning and Neural

Networks for EEG data analysis. Section 3 provides a short review of the GCN fundamentals. Section 4 discusses the current literature on the applications of GCNs to EEG data analysis. Finally, Section 5 provides our final conclusions.

2. Neural Networks for EEG data processing: general panorama

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), specially Deep Learning (DL) architectures, have become the forefront of Artificial Intelligence. In this section we provide a general panorama of their applications to EEG data processing in order to set the stage for the specific contributions of Graph Neural Networks (GNN). First we comment on the bibliographic search carried out. Next, we describe the general findings in terms of computational architectures and clinical targets of EEG data analysis. Being data oriented Artificial Intelligence techniques, ANNs need big amounts of data in order to achieve competitive performances. Hence the high value of extensive data repositories such as PhysioNet (<https://physionet.org/about/database/>) for the development of new architectures and applications to EEG data.

2.1. Bibliographic search

We have carried out searches in PUBMED, sciencedirect, springerlink, and ieeexplore using the terms “EGG GNN GCN Neural Networks” in order to get an extensive covering of possible publications. The

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: manuel.grana@ehu.eus (M. Graña), igone.morais@ehu.eus (I. Morais-Quilez).

Fig. 1. Evolution of the number of publications in PUBMED on EEG data analysis by Neural Networks.

Fig. 2. Distribution of the number of papers according to the clinical target.

most comprehensive results were produced by PUBMED search, which produced over five thousand references that show the intense interest of EEG data analysis by advanced computational methods. Fig. 1 shows the growth in the number of publications on Neural Networks applied to EEG data in the last years. We collected 1282 publications in this area of work. GNNs are a relatively recent development in the field of Artificial Intelligence, hence most of the references found are in the last few years. After filtering by abstract contents, we retained 35 references strictly dealing with GNN and related deep learning architectures for the analysis of EEG data. One of them was discarded because of its very low quality, so we the review finally deals with 34 references.

2.2. Clinical and research targets

Fig. 2 shows the summary information about the distribution of the literature over the most relevant clinical and research targets. The most salient areas of research are related to the study of brain functional connectivity [6] as a biomarker for diverse conditions, pathological or not, such as the effect of physical exercise on brain functional connectivity [7]. Studies on epilepsy focused on the detection/prediction of seizures is one of the major areas of application of EEG data recording. Works devoted to the characterization of epilepsy are usually focused on structural analysis of brain functional connectivity [8] or the localization of onset regions in the brain [9]. Prediction of seizures is tricky

Fig. 3. Distribution of the number of papers according to the computational area.

Architecture.png

Fig. 4. Distribution of the number of papers according to the ANN architecture.

because of the very low signal-to-noise ratio of relevant signal cues and the high dependency on individual characteristics, so it is still an open research area despite intense research [10,11].

Another very relevant area of research is Brain Computer Interfaces (BCI) that deals with EEG signals decoding for diverse applications, like discovering covert attention focus [12]. Specifically, many works are devoted to motor imagery decoding (i.e. decoding the intention to move some part of the body) [13–15] that can be used for rehabilitation after stroke [16] or after spinal cord injuries [17], or the control of robotic assistant devices [18]. Emotion decoding [19,20] is a very salient area of research related to BCI, with applications in psychological and clinical research, such as depression assessment [21]. The use of EEG in psychiatric and psychological research has a long tradition, such as in the study of schizophrenia [22,23] including diagnostic assistance [24]. Other research topics are developmental

syndromes, such as attention deficit [25], and autism [26–28]. Research into neurodegenerative diseases and dementias has been also a major topic of EEG related research, tackling studies on Alzheimer’s Disease (AD) [29–31], Parkinson’s Disease (PD) [32,33], and bipolar disorder (BPD) [34,35]. The study of sleep disorders using EEG data is another classical research area [36] that has reached clinical practice. In sleep research, EEG is often combined with other physiological signals, such as electrocardiography (ECG) and respiration [37].

2.3. Computational architectures

Fig. 3 shows the distribution of papers according to the computational areas. Machine learning has been a great contributor to EEG data analysis in the last decades [38], mostly for classification tasks associated with BCI or clinical diagnostic assistance. Early approaches applying graph theoretic measures for the identification of biomarkers

Overall distribution of papers over clinical targets and computational architectures

Clinical Target	GNN	GCN	CNN	GAN	GAT	LSTM	CNN w/ResNet	BiGRU	MLP	FRNN	Res-Net	RNN	ESN	DNN	Auto-enc	Network w/Network	VGG	Deep-Like	Inception	ResNeXt	MobileNet	CapSNet/Network	TNN	BEFT	MCDN	R-CNN	BFN	DBN	Asynchronous	Biometric Neural Network	Other				
Epilepsy	1	5	107	5	36	68	21	1	1	0	2	7	7	0	5	0	7	204	1	3	0	0	0	0	2	16	2	2	0	0	3	17	110		
Stroke	1	6	36	6	49	57	19	1	0	0	1	7	20	7	2	5	0	100	1	3	0	0	0	0	107	14	3	109	0	2	2	19	75		
Parkinson	0	0	10	1	6	6	4	0	0	0	1	0	4	0	0	0	0	22	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	1	7	0	1	0	4	10			
Emotions	1	7	51	5	14	35	12	1	0	1	1	5	6	6	3	3	0	1	87	0	1	0	0	1	1	6	1	46	0	1	1	4	92		
Depression	0	0	26	1	12	17	9	0	0	0	1	1	9	2	1	1	0	144	0	1	0	1	0	0	4	4	1	26	0	0	0	3	18		
Relaxation	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	29		
ADHD	0	0	5	0	4	3	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	5	0	0	0	0	10		
Attention-Deficit	1	0	5	1	6	6	1	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	5	0	1	0	0	10		
Sleep	1	3	37	3	25	34	17	1	0	0	0	3	5	0	2	2	0	112	1	2	0	3	0	0	10	1	0	50	0	1	0	0	112		
Alzheimer	0	0	10	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	118	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	12		
Fatigue	1	1	18	3	5	13	4	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	20		
P300 Indicator	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33		
Drowsiness	0	0	1	0	3	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	12	0	1	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	8	0	0	1	12	15		
Brain Activity	2	1	76	7	7	89	11	0	0	0	0	5	12	0	0	4	0	1	205	0	3	0	0	0	4	4	0	1	4	2	1	13	205		
Dementia	8	2	4	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	12	
Alzheimer	1	1	6	3	14	16	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	10	
Delirium	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	4		
Autism	0	0	5	0	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	12
Speech	0	0	19	0	4	17	4	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	0	3	39	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	19	0	0	1	2	39		
Auditory	2	0	11	1	6	18	2	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	28	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	38	
Auditory Attention	1	0	8	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
Brain function	3	10	66	11	158	158	8	0	0	0	1	0	3	5	2	3	0	5	196	0	4	1	0	2	0	1	0	2	0	1	2	25	180		
Visual attention	0	1	15	0	16	8	5	0	1	0	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	22	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	10	
Tactile attention	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
Dyslexia	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
Biometric System	0	0	1	0	3	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
Biometry	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
Consciousness	0	1	1	1	9	11	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	
Brain injury	0	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	
Anesthetic State	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2		
Central Ischemia	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
Stroke	0	1	12	0	16	16	4	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	15	
Unconsciousness	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Ischemia	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
Schizophrenia	1	0	7	0	3	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
Mental States	2	5	94	5	11	62	16	0	0	1	2	6	3	0	1	5	0	4	12	1	3	0	1	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	63
Mental fitness	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
Bipolar	4	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	1	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
Bipolar Disorder	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	
Neurological Diseases	0	0	6	0	0	5	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	5	
BCI	1	7	7	10	16	51	21	0	1	2	2	0	6	2	7	3	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	4

Fig. 5. Overall distribution of papers over clinical targets and computational architectures.

in the functional connectivity matrices derived from EEG data [39,40] have been superseded by data driven machine learning techniques that validate the biomarkers by the classification performance achieved. In this paradigm, biomarkers were identified by feature extraction processes, but often they lack interpretability from the clinical or psychiatric/psychological point of view. This black box situation is even worse for the actual deep learning approaches, hence the emphasis on interpretable architectures and results [41]. In fact, deep learning approaches are the dominant [42,43] ones in the literature.

Fig. 4 shows the specific distribution of neural network and deep learning architectures dealing with EEG data analysis for the diverse research targets. Fig. 5 shows the overall two dimensional distribution of papers over the clinical targets and deep learning architectures. As in many other areas, transfer learning has been exploited to some extent [44], which explains the occurrence of pretrained networks in the figures. A big concentration of papers appear for some topics and computational architectures, such as the application of CNNs for BCI, epilepsy, sleep and brain function in general. EEG data processing has been an early adopted of CNN architectures for diverse tasks, such as the prediction of memory performance in an auditory task [45], or the screening of depression [46]. CNN architectures have also been hybridized [47] with other deep learning approaches, such as LSTMs [48]. In many studies, CNNs are used to process the brain functional connectivity matrices derived from EEG channels, while recursive networks are used for feature extraction from each channel time series. Recurrent CNNs (RCNN) try to carry out simultaneously the temporal and spatial processes [49]. Recently, attention modules are increasingly used in order to detect specific events that may be relevant biomarkers [50], and to the adoption of generative adversarial network (GAN) approaches that combine synthetic and real spectrograms to improve performance and to anticipate unlikely events [51]. Some exotic architectures have also been proposed, such as the sequence-to-sequence translation for sleep stage encoding [52].

3. Short review of GCNs

Early attempts to apply neural networks to direct acyclic graphs [53] in order to classify non-euclidean structures motivated a decade later some early studies on graph convolutional networks (GCNs) [54–56]. GCNs try to generalize 2D convolutions in order to follow the inspiration of successful CNNs for non Euclidean domains [1]. The underlying analogy is that the pixels in an image are nodes in a graph where their neighbors are determined by the shape of the convolution

kernel applied to the image which also contains the weight specification for the computation of the weighted average of the neighborhood at each pixel. Analogously, graph convolution could be defined as the weighted average of each node’s neighborhood, which can be of different sizes and topologies for different nodes.

The so called spatial-based GNNs define graph convolutions by rearranging graph nodes into certain grid forms which can be processed by standard CNNs [57,58]. The early approach to the definition of spectral based graph convolutions were defined on the basis of graph Fourier transforms computing the spectrum of the graph Laplacian [59], which has been followed by a host of improvements, approximate methods, and extensions of spectral GNNs [60–63] aiming to reduce the computational complexity to the order of the number of nodes.

Let us defined a graph convolution operator “*G,” operating over a signal $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ in the spatial space with a kernel θ as follows:

$$\theta * Gx = \theta(L)x = \theta(U\Lambda U^T)x = U\theta(\Lambda)U^T x, \quad (1)$$

where the matrix of eigenvectors $U \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ of the normalized graph Laplacian $L = I_n - D^{-\frac{1}{2}}WD^{-\frac{1}{2}} = U\Lambda U^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the graph Fourier basis. In this expression, I_n is an identity matrix of size n , $D \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the diagonal degree matrix defined by $D_{ij} = \sum_j W_{ij}$, the diagonal matrix $\Lambda \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ contains the eigenvalues of L , and the filter $\theta(\Lambda)$ is also a diagonal matrix. According to [64], filtering a signal defined over a graph domain x with a kernel θ is achieved by multiplication between θ and the graph Fourier transform $U^T x$. Chebyshev polynomials and first-order approximations were introduced [62]

Table 1
Summary applications of GNN to EEG.

	GCN	R-NN + GCN	GCN-TC	AD-GCN-CNN	GGN	MTS-DGCHN
BCI	[66–70]	[71,72]	[17,73]			[74]
Fatigue	[75]					
Sleep	[76]		[77–79]			
Epilepsy	[80–84]				[85]	
Emotion	[86–92]		[93]	[94]		
Biometrics	[95]					
AD	[30]		[96]			
Schizophrenia	[97]					

Note: AD: Alzheimer’s Disease. BCI: brain computer interface. GCN includes references to GNNs. GCN-TC: GCN and temporal convolution. AD-GCN-CNN: GCN and CNN plus Adversarial Domain Adaption with a Level-wise Attention Mechanism. GGN : Graph generative neural network. MTS-DGCHN : multi-scale temporal self-attention and dynamical graph convolution hybrid network. R-NN + GCN : combines recurrent NN like GRU or LSTM with GCN.

be rewritten to:

$$\Theta * \mathcal{G}x = \Theta(L)x \approx \sum_{k=0}^{K-1} \theta_k T_k(L)x, \tag{4}$$

where $T_k(L) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the Chebyshev polynomial of order k evaluated at the scaled Laplacian $L = 2L/\lambda_{\max} - I_n$. By recursive application of Eq. (4) the cost of Eq. (1) can be reduced to $\mathcal{O}(K|\epsilon|)$. Furthermore, a layer-wise linear system can be defined stacking localized graph convolutional layers [62], and we can assume $\lambda_{\max} \approx 2$ due to the standard scaling and normalization carried out in neural network training. Eq. (4) can be further simplified to

$$\Theta * \mathcal{G}x \approx \theta_0 x + \theta_1 \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_{\max}} L - I_n \right) x \approx \theta_0 x + \theta_1 \left(D^{-\frac{1}{2}} W D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) x, \tag{5}$$

where the θ_0 and θ_1 parameters can be replaced by a single parameter by letting $\theta_0 = -\theta_1 = \theta$ in order to stabilize numerical processes. A further implication can be achieved by normalizing W and D separately computing $W = W - I_n$ and $D_{ii} = \sum_j W_{ij}$. The graph convolution of (1) can be simplified into the following expression:

$$\Theta * \mathcal{G}x = \theta \left(I_n + D^{-\frac{1}{2}} W D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) x = \theta \left(D - \frac{1}{2} W D - \frac{1}{2} \right) x. \tag{6}$$

In order to extend the convolution to a signal with C_i channels, i.e. $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times C_i}$, the graph convolution can be generalized to

$$y_j = \sum_{i=1}^{C_i} \Theta_{ij}(L)x_i \in \mathbb{R}^n, 1 \leq j \leq C_0, \tag{7}$$

where y_j is the output after graph convolution, C_i and C_0 are the sizes of the input and output of the feature maps, respectively, and $\Theta_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^K$ are the $C_i \times C_0$ vectors of Chebyshev coefficients. Analogously, the graph convolution can be extended to 2D and 3D variables. In the case of EEG data, channel features can be composed into 2D frames which are the input to the GCN.

4. Applications of GCNs to EEG data processing

Table 1 summarizes the findings of our bibliographic search after extracting papers that strictly propose GNNs for EEG data processing. The general approach of the application of GNNs to EEG data is based on the computation of the brain functional connectivity matrix based on some similarity measure among channels, which can be done in the temporal dimension or on the result of band pass filtering after frequency transformation. Sometimes, instead of the band pass filtering some DL approach, such as CNNs or recurrent networks are applied to extract channel features which are then used to build the brain connectivity matrix for the GNNs. A diversity of similarity measures can be used to build the channel adjacency matrix that is the surrogate for the brain connectivity matrix. Some similarity measures that have been exploited [66,96,98,99] are the following: (1) Pearson correlation coefficient, (2) Magnitude squared coherence which is a linear method to estimate the interconnections between the power spectral density of two signals in the frequency domain. (3) Imaginary part of coherence between signals, (4) Wavelet coherence that provides a qualitative

representation of the dynamic relations in the time–frequency domain between signals. (5) Phase synchronization assumes which can provide connectivity information of two oscillation signals without amplitude synchronization. (6) Phase lag index that captures the asymmetry of the distribution of phase differences between two signals. It is given by the relative phase difference between the two signals. (7) Mutual Information similarity. (8) Synchronization likelihood measure gives a straightforward normalized estimate of the dynamical interdependencies between two or more simultaneously recorded time series [100]. (9) Weighted phase lag index [101] extends phase lag index measure, by introducing a phase-difference weighting normalization.

A rather general view of the basic GNN architecture applied to EEG data is shown in Fig. 6, where the graph input usually corresponds to the brain functional connectivity matrix. Often, the node information is enriched by some features extracted from the electrode signal by 1D CNNs or other 1D feature extraction process. The number of nodes of the input graph and the input feature vector size are denoted in the figure by \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{m} , respectively. Each layer of the GNN corresponds to a batch of graph convolution operators followed by ReLu activation functions and dropout/pooling operators that can be applied separately to the graph nodes and the feature vectors. Thus, the graphs are progressively reduced in both aspects at ensuing layers, until all the information is pooled together into fully connected layers that implement the final softmax based classification decision into patients with clinical labels (CL) and healthy controls (HC). Diverse hybridizations for specific clinical target applications will be described below.

4.1. Sleep

One of the most important tasks in sleep analysis and assessment for disease diagnosis is sleep stage classification. Though conventional machine learning approaches have been successful to some degree, GNNs can provide significant contributions. Specifically, a multi-view spatiotemporal GCN has been proposed [77] that achieves competitive results on benchmarks datasets. The approach uses two graph adjacency matrices, one based on signal similarity, and the other on physical distance between the electrodes. Besides, temporal CNN is used to extract features from the channels as attributes to the graph nodes. An attention mechanism is trained to capture the most relevant spatiotemporal information aiming to obtain subject independent sleep features. A multimodal approach exploiting different types of multi-channel bio-signals has been also proposed [78] to classify sleep stages using multiple cues. Again, node features are extracted by CNNs. The approach focus on the extraction of transition rules among sleep stages from the GNN and temporal CNN features. Finally, a proposal [79] that combines temporal CNN, spatial GNNs, and intertemporal attention blocks designed to detect long range dependencies between the electrodes that are meaningful for the classification of sleep stages.

Fig. 6. General GNN architecture for EEG data processing.

4.2. Epilepsy

Prediction of upcoming seizure onsets plays a key role in BCI-aided epilepsy treatment systems that provide appropriate therapeutic electrical stimulus to prevent the seizure. General GNN approaches [81, 82] have shown promising results. However, the signal patterns in preictal periods are highly individual-dependent and difficult to discriminate from the background signal clutter, in contrast with the very salient signal features in ictal periods. The high dependency of preictal signals on the individual is a strong limitation to the application of machine learning approaches, and GNNs as well. The joint graph structure and representation learning network (JGRN) is a novel proposal [80] automatically learns a patient-specific graph in a data-driven way. This approach builds global-local GNNs learning simultaneously the graph structure and the connection weights, achieving remarkable improvements over state-of-the-art approaches in seizure prediction. Another relevant approach to patient-specific EEG seizure predictor [83] consists of a novel spatio-temporal-spectral hierarchical graph convolutional network endowed with an active preictal interval learning scheme. The proposed framework first characterizes an epileptic cortex under different concurrent rhythms inferring a hierarchical graph. Temporal dependencies and spatial couplings are extracted by a spectral-temporal convolutional neural network and a variant self-gating mechanism, respectively. The hierarchical graph convolutional network identifies critical intrarhythm spatiotemporal properties to predict seizures. Another recent approach [85] is graph-generative neural network model for the dynamic discovery of brain functional connectivity. The graph generation module includes the training of GNNs that are extracted from adjacency matrix of the EEG data to learn the parameters of some mix-Gaussian distribution, which allows for the flexibility required to recognize preictal signals that change inter-individual. On the basis of this probabilistic modeling, a Gumbel-Sampler generates the edges of latent graphs that can be matched to the EEG data by an attention decoder module. Thus, the approach tries to predict the short time graphs of preictal periods.

4.3. Emotion

There is a diversity of approaches to evoke and decode emotions from EEG data. Works reported on GNNs for emotion recognition deal with a rather limited set of emotions. Oil paintings have been tried as emotion triggering stimuli (positive, neutral, negative) [90]. In this work the role of GNNs was to validate the oil paintings as emotional stimuli by the ability to decode the emotion induced by the painting over the EEG of the observer. Music is often used as the emotional stimuli. For instance, a cohort of 6 women and 10 men

listening to emotional music is used in the study about the emotion recognition by dynamic GNNs using as input the EEG signal sources recovered by a Bayesian method [86]. Besides, results on public SEED and DEAP datasets confirmed the superior classification performance of the approach. A different approach, based on the learning and iterative update of the brain connectivity matrix as input to the GNN [87], reports also good performance on the SEED (stimuli were happy, sad, and neutral video clips) database. In a different vein, a semisupervised approach is proposed to carry out sample classification from a small seed of labeled EEG samples in the SEED and SEED IV (happy, sad, neutral, fear emotions) datasets Li et al. [88]. In this approach, the graph is built by computing the similarities between the features extracted from the EEG data of each sample, thus the GNN is used to propagate the sample labels. Over the same datasets, another GNN approach Li et al. [89] is based on the dynamic construction of brain connectivity graphs from the EEG signals by a self-organizing approach. In essence, each level of a CNN architecture applied to the EEG channels produces the feature vectors of the nodes of a specific GNN. The result of all independent GNNs is aggregated for emotion classification. Over the same datasets, another study proposes a multilayer GCN followed by a CNN with style reconfiguration modules between layers Bao et al. [93], while yet another proposes that GCN-CNN features are processed by an adversarial domain adaption module endowed with a level-wise attention mechanism aiming to obtain more transferable features. Reporting results over the DEAP dataset, another approach Zhao et al. [92] proposes a coherence based node clustering in order to apply a novel multi-pooling of the graph between layers of the GCN. A big departure in the construction of the brain connectivity matrix is the use of Granger causality as the similarity measure between EEG channels Zhang et al. [91]. The authors compute the Granger causality at each conventional frequency band and fuse them to build the binary causal connectivity matrix. Additionally, they use differential entropy features to characterize each channel and the corresponding node for GCN operation.

4.4. Brain computer interfaces

Brain computer interfaces (BCI) have interest in diverse domains, such as rehabilitation after neural system damage and neural interfaces for advanced orthopedics. The hypothesis is that EEG data can be used to decode the intention of movement in order to generate control commands to external assistive equipment. Decoding motor imagery has been reported with the bare application of GCNs over standard Pearson correlation functional connectivity matrices over a large cohort of 109 volunteers imaging simple hand and feet motions [68]. Computer vision object detection has been used in order to enhance

control of an external supernumerary robotic limb by motor imagery classification using a GNN with recurrent neural network temporal feature extraction [72]. The motor intention of four fine parts movements (shoulder, elbow, wrist, hand) have been decoded using GCNs over several variations of the functional connectivity matrix computed using different similarity measures [66]. Quick decoding is also necessary for live interaction with external devices. A blend of bidirectional LSTMs (for time series translation into informative codes) and GNNs (for the recognition of brain functional states) has achieved competitive results a over public dataset [71]. Aiming to develop assistive rehabilitation devices for patients with spinal-cord injuries, [17] have proposed a modified GNN, which consists of a preprocessing step applying a modified S-transform to the EEG data [102]. Brain connectivity matrix is built using Pearson correlation and it is enriched with the results of the modified S-transform, becoming the input of the GNN. Training data is captured following a classical epoch data capture interleaving resting and imaging periods, compromising real time operation. Another approach to improve the performance of GNNs in motor imagery decoding consists in the dynamical updating of the EEG channel adjacency matrix on the basis of cosine similarity [70], outperforming state-of-the-art approaches over public dataset benchmarks.

Over general standard experimental data on spelling and typing, GNN have been shown to outperform [69] other approaches such as CNNs and AutoBayes. Color decoding from EEG data has been achieved with GCNs [67] reporting decreasing performance as the time from the encoding increases. Authors claim that color decoding could an additional indication about the memory performance of the subject. Decoding stereograms from EEG signals (which can help the ophthalmologists to diagnose strabismus patients with impaired communication) has been reported [74] by the application of an innovative multi-scale temporal self-attention and dynamical graph convolution hybrid network. Where the role of the dynamical GCN is to capture the time evolving spatial functional relationships between different EEG electrodes in order to explore their optimal intrinsic relationship on the basis of the features extracted by the 1D convolution and self-attention modules. Detecting the appearance of a target in a video recording on the basis of single-trial P3 peak detection has been reported [73] by a GNN architecture enriched by 1D CNN applied to the channels independently.

Detection of driver's fatigue is another BCI task that may have a strong impact in the lives of public. The literature on the application of GNNs to this task is limited. A study involving a small cohort of student volunteers in a simulation environment [75] reported that GNNs improve over standard approaches based on conventional machine learning. Specifically, the authors use partial coherence as the similarity measure to build up the adjacency matrix that is the input to the GNN. Finally, we would like to consider human identification using EEG as a biometric signal. Some works Tian et al. [95] have shown the potential of GCNs for this task, evaluating a number of similarity measures in the construction of the functional connectivity graph with promising results.

4.5. Psychiatric diseases

One of the salient applications of EEG data processing is the search for psychiatric disease biomarkers that may help to understand the underlying causes and to introduce early diagnostic tools. In the case of schizophrenia patients, Mismatch negativity (MMN) has been proposed as an electrophysiological indicator [103]. MMN is an event-related potential (ERP) feature related to the pre-attentive auditory processing capability whose duration has been found to be reduced in first-episode schizophrenia patients [104]. Following this hypothesis, GNNs have been applied to the discrimination of healthy controls (HC), first-episode and chronic schizophrenia patients over a cohort of 120 subjects [97]. The reported results show that GNNs based on spectral and temporal brain connectivity networks achieve better performance

than the classical SVM approach based on graph global and local features.

In the context of population aging in western countries, the prevalence of Alzheimer's disease (AD) dementia is growing steadily. AD results memory loss and cognitive impairments. It is well known that the pathological progression of AD leads to cortical disconnections that can be detected on EEG data as functional connectivity alterations [105]. A novel spatial-temporal GCN has been proposed to discriminate AD patients from HC over a cohort of 19 AD patients and 20 HC participants [96]. The study involves the comparison of six kinds of channel adjacency matrices of brain connectivity computed by difference similarity measures. The approach exploits network features as well as channel specific temporal features. It is shown to improve significantly over a temporal CNN approach.

5. Conclusions

EEG data has been used at the clinical, industrial and research levels for a wide variety of applications. At clinical level they are routinely used for sleep related diseases. Industrial applications include drowsiness assessment for drivers and machine operators. In research EEG data have been used in the search for biomarkers of several psychiatric conditions. ANNs have been extensively applied trying to extract relevant features or to carry out health control versus patient discrimination with limited results in some syndromes.

Though GNNs are already becoming a mature technology, their application to EEG data processing is relatively recent. The number of published works up to this date are limited, but they will be growing fast in the coming years because GNNs fit very nicely in the framework of brain connectivity analysis, which provides an additional dimension to exploit the EEG data. Most salient applications are brain computer interfaces (BCI), emotion decoding, and seizure prediction in epilepsy. There is a growing interest in the potential for assisted diagnostic systems in psychiatric diseases, including dementias, and development syndromes, such as autism spectrum conditions.

The application of GNNs to EEG data has fostered a wave of fundamental architectural innovations in the area of deep learning, including the hybridization with recurrent or classical convolutional architectures. Recently, the proposal of generative GNNs has been influential in order to attack the data scarcity problem in the EEG datasets, were the number of samples, i.e. healthy controls and patients, is often short though the size of the data recordings is large. Also, the recent transformers architectures, coming from natural language processing, that provide clever attention mechanisms are entering the design of GNNs in order to have a direct mechanism for the identification of EEG-based biomarkers. Thus, the main directions for future research are driven by these two axis of innovations in the GNNs and hybrid architectures.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Manuel grana reports financial support was provided by Spain Ministry of Science and Innovation. Igone Morais reports financial support was provided by Spain Ministry of Science and Innovation. assistant editor

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Funding acknowledgments

The first author has received research funds from the Basque Government as the head of the Grupo de Inteligencia Computacional, Universidad del País Vasco, UPV/EHU since 2007 until 2025. The current code for the grant is IT1689-22. Additionally, the author participates in Elkartek projects KK-2022/00051 and KK-2021/00070. The Spanish MICIN has also granted a research project under code PID2020-116346GB-I00. Second author has a PIF grant from the PICIN with code PRE2021-096876.

References

texto

- [1] Zonghan Wu, Shirui Pan, Fengwen Chen, Guodong Long, Chengqi Zhang, Philip S. Yu, A comprehensive survey on graph neural networks, *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw. Learn. Syst.* 32 (1) (2021) 4–24, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNNLS.2020.2978386>.
- [2] Jaap C Reijneveld, Sophie C Ponten, Henk W Berendse, Cornelis J Stam, The application of graph theoretical analysis to complex networks in the brain, *J. Clin. Neurophysiol.* 118 (11) (2007) 2317–2331, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2007.08.010>, (ISSN: 1388-2457 (Print); 1388-2457 (Linking)).
- [3] *Electrical Neuroimaging*, Cambridge University Press, 2009, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511596889>.
- [4] Una Smailovic, Thomas Koenig, Ingemar Kåreholt, Thomas Andersson, Milica Gregoric Kramberger, Bengt Winblad, Vesna Jelic, Quantitative EEG power and synchronization correlate with Alzheimer's disease CSF biomarkers, *Neurobiol. Aging* 63 (2018) 88–95, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2017.11.005>, (ISSN: 1558-1497 (Electronic); 0197-4580 (Linking)).
- [5] Laura Astolfi, F De Vico Fallani, F Cincotti, D Mattia, L Bianchi, M G Marciani, S Salinari, A Colosimo, A Tocci, R Soranzo, F Babiloni, Neural basis for brain responses to TV commercials: a high-resolution EEG study, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* 16 (6) (2008) 522–531, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2008.2009784>, (ISSN: 1558-0210 (Electronic); 1534-4320 (Linking)).
- [6] Cornelis J. Stam, Jaap C. Reijneveld, Graph theoretical analysis of complex networks in the brain, *Nonlinear Biomed. Phys.* 1 (1) (2007) 3, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1753-4631-1-3>, (ISSN: 1753-4631 (Electronic); 1753-4631 (Linking)).
- [7] Keita Kamijo, Yuji Takeda, Charles H. Hillman, The relation of physical activity to functional connectivity between brain regions, *J. Clin. Neurophysiol.* 122 (1) (2011) 81–89, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2010.06.007>, (ISSN: 1872-8952 (Electronic); 1388-2457 (Linking)).
- [8] Fenglai Xiao, Du Lei, Dongmei An, Lei Li, Sihang Chen, Fuqin Chen, Tianhua Yang, Jiechuan Ren, Xiaoqi Huang, Qiyong Gong, Dong Zhou, Functional brain connectome and sensorimotor networks in rolandic epilepsy, *Epilepsy Res.* 113 (2015) 113–125, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.eplepsyres.2015.03.015>, (ISSN: 1872-6844 (Electronic); 0920-1211 (Linking)).
- [9] Marleen C Tjepkema-Cloostermans, Rafael C V de Carvalho, Michel J A M van Putten, Deep learning for detection of focal epileptiform discharges from scalp EEG recordings, *J. Clin. Neurophysiol.* 129 (10) (2018) 2191–2196, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2018.06.024>, (ISSN: 1872-8952 (Electronic); 1388-2457 (Linking)).
- [10] Xiaozeng Gao, Xiaoyan Yan, Ping Gao, Xiujiang Gao, Shubo Zhang, Automatic detection of epileptic seizure based on approximate entropy, recurrence quantification analysis and convolutional neural networks, *Artif. Intell. Med.* 102 (2020) 101711, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.artmed.2019.101711>, (ISSN: 1873-2860 (Electronic); 0933-3657 (Linking)).
- [11] Iostas Í Tsiouris, Vasileios C Pezoulas, Michalis Zervakis, Spiros Konitsiotis, Dimitrios D Koutsouris, Dimitrios I Fotiadis, A long short-term memory deep learning network for the prediction of epileptic seizures using EEG signals, *Comput. Biol. Med.* 99 (2018) 24–37, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2018.05.019>, (ISSN: 1879-0534 (Electronic); 0010-4825 (Linking)).
- [12] Amr Farahat, Christoph Reichert, Catherine M Sweeney-Reed, Hermann Hinrichs, Convolutional neural networks for decoding of covert attention focus and saliency maps for EEG feature visualization, *J. Neural Eng.* 16 (6) (2019) 066010, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ab3bb4>, (ISSN: 1741-2552 (Electronic); 1741-2552 (Linking)).
- [13] Lorena Santamaria, Christopher James, Using brain connectivity metrics from synchrostates to perform motor imagery classification in EEG-based BCI systems, *Healthc. Technol. Lett.* 5 (3) (2018) 88–93, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1049/hlt.2017.0049>, (ISSN: 2053-3713 (Print); 2053-3713 (Electronic); 2053-3713 (Linking)).
- [14] Yousef Rezaei Tabar, Ugur Halici, A novel deep learning approach for classification of EEG motor imagery signals, *J. Neural Eng.* 14 (1) (2017) 016003, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1741-2560/14/1/016003>, (ISSN: 1741-2552 (Electronic); 1741-2552 (Linking)).
- [15] Juntao Xue, Feiyue Ren, Xinlin Sun, Miaomiao Yin, Jialing Wu, Chao Ma, Zhongke Gao, A multifrequency brain network-based deep learning framework for motor imagery decoding, *Neural Plast.* 2020 (2020) 8863223, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2020/8863223>, (ISSN: 1687-5443 (Electronic); 2090-5904 (Print); 1687-5443 (Linking)).
- [16] Ping-Ju Lin, Tianyu Jia, Chong Li, Tianyi Li, Chao Qian, Zhibin Li, Yu Pan, Linhong Ji, CNN-based prognosis of BCI rehabilitation using EEG from first session BCI training, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* 29 (2021) 1936–1943, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2021.3112167>, (ISSN: 1558-0210 (Electronic); 1534-4320 (Linking)).
- [17] Fangzhou Xu, Jincheng Li, Gege Dong, Jianfei Li, Xinyi Chen, Jianqun Zhu, Jinglu Hu, Yang Zhang, Shouwei Yue, Dong Wen, Jiancai Leng, EEG decoding method based on multi-feature information fusion for spinal cord injury, *Neural Netw.* 156 (2022) 135–151, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2022.09.016>, (ISSN: 1879-2782 (Electronic); 0893-6080 (Linking)).
- [18] Ji-Hoon Jeong, Kyung-Hwan Shim, Dong-Joo Kim, Seong-Whan Lee, Brain-controlled robotic arm system based on multi-directional CNN-BiLSTM network using EEG signals, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* 28 (5) (2020) 1226–1238, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2020.2981659>, (ISSN: 1558-0210 (Electronic); 1534-4320 (Linking)).
- [19] Nagarajan Ganapathy, Ramakrishnan Swaminathan, Emotion recognition using electrodermal activity signals and multiscale deep convolution neural network, *Stud. Health Technol. Inform.* 258 (2019) 140, (ISSN: 1879-8365 (Electronic); 0926-9630 (Linking)).
- [20] Mehmet Akif Ozdemir, Murside Degirmenci, Elif Izci, Aydin Akan, EEG-based emotion recognition with deep convolutional neural networks, *Biomed. Tech. (Berl)* (2020) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1515/bmt-2019-0306>, (ISSN: 1862-278X (Electronic); 0013-5585 (Linking)).
- [21] Hongli Chang, Yuan Zong, Wenming Zheng, Chuangao Tang, Jie Zhu, Xuejun Li, Depression assessment method: An EEG emotion recognition framework based on spatiotemporal neural network, *Front. Psychiatry* 12 (2021) 837149, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.837149>, (ISSN: 1664-0640 (Print); 1664-0640 (Electronic); 1664-0640 (Linking)).
- [22] Mahdi Jalili, Maria G. Knyazeva, EEG-based functional networks in schizophrenia, *Comput. Biol. Med.* 41 (12) (2011) 1178–1186, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2011.05.004>, (ISSN: 1879-0534 (Electronic); 0010-4825 (Linking)).
- [23] Kuldeep Singh, Sukhjeet Singh, Jyoteesh Malhotra, Spectral features based convolutional neural network for accurate and prompt identification of schizophrenic patients, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. H* 235 (2) (2021) 167–184, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0954411920966937>, (ISSN: 2041-3033 (Electronic); 0954-4119 (Linking)).
- [24] A I Korda, E Ventouras, P Asvestas, Maida Toumaian, G K Matsopoulos, N Smyrnis, Convolutional neural network propagation on electroencephalographic scalograms for detection of schizophrenia, *J. Clin. Neurophysiol.* 139 (2022) 90–105, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2022.04.010>, (ISSN: 1872-8952 (Electronic); 1388-2457 (Linking)).
- [25] Pablo Bartfeld, Agustín Petroni, Sandra Báez, Hugo Urquina, Mariano Sigman, Marcelo Cetkovich, Teresa Torralva, Fernando Torrente, Alicia Lischinsky, Xavier Castellanos, Facundo Manes, Agustín Ibañez, Functional connectivity and temporal variability of brain connections in adults with attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder and bipolar disorder, *Neuropsychobiology* 69 (2) (2014) 65–75, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1159/000356964>, (ISSN: 1423-0224 (Electronic); 0302-282X (Linking)).
- [26] Noura Alotaibi, Koushik Maharatra, Classification of autism spectrum disorder from EEG-based functional brain connectivity analysis, *Neural Comput.* 33 (7) (2021) 1914–1941, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1162/neco.1a.10194>, (ISSN: 1530-888X (Electronic); 0899-7667 (Linking)).
- [27] Habib Adabi Ardakani, Maryam Taghizadeh, Farzaneh Shayegh, Diagnosis of autism disorder based on deep network trained by augmented EEG signals, *Int. J. Neural Syst.* 32 (11) (2022) 2250046, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1142/S0129065722500460>, (ISSN: 1793-6462 (Electronic); 0129-0657 (Linking)).
- [28] Maria Boersma, Chantal Kemmer, Marcel A de Reus, Gusje Collin, Tineke M Snijders, Dennis Hofman, Jan K Buitelaar, Cornelis J Stam, Martijn P van den Heuvel, Disrupted functional brain networks in autistic toddlers, *Brain Connect* 3 (1) (2013) 41–49, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1089/brain.2012.0127>, (ISSN: 2158-0022 (Electronic); 2158-0014 (Linking)).
- [29] Xiaojun Bi, Haibo Wang, Early Alzheimer's disease diagnosis based on EEG spectral images using deep learning, *Neural Netw.* 114 (2019) 119–135, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2019.02.005>, (ISSN: 1879-2782 (Electronic); 0893-6080 (Linking)).
- [30] Dominik Klepl, Fei He, Min Wu, Daniel J Blackburn, Ptolemaios Sarrigiannis, EEG-based graph neural network classification of Alzheimer's disease: An empirical evaluation of functional connectivity methods, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* 30 (2022) 2651–2660, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2022.3204913>, (ISSN: 1558-0210 (Electronic); 1534-4320 (Linking)).
- [31] C J Stam, B F Jones, G Nolte, M Breakspear, Ph Scheltens, Small-world networks and functional connectivity in Alzheimer's disease, *Cereb Cortex* 17 (1) (2007) 92–99, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhj127>, (ISSN: 1047-3211 (Print); 1047-3211 (Linking)).

- [32] Kim T E Olde Dubbelink, Arjan Hillebrand, Diederick Stoffers, Jan Berend Deijen, Jos W R Twisk, Cornelis J Stam, Henk W Berendse, Disrupted brain network topology in Parkinson's disease: a longitudinal magnetoencephalography study, *Brain* 137 (Pt 1) (2014) 197–207, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/brain/awt316>, (ISSN: 1460-2156 (Electronic); 0006-8950 (Linking)).
- [33] Gajanan S Revankar, Yuta Kajiyama, Noriaki Hattori, Tetsuya Shimokawa, Tomohito Nakano, Masahito Mihara, Etsuro Mori, Hideki Mochizuki, Prestimulus low-alpha frontal networks are associated with pareidolia in Parkinson's disease, *Brain Connect* 11 (9) (2021) 772–782, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1089/brain.2020.0992>, (ISSN: 2158-0022 (Electronic); 2158-0014 (Linking)).
- [34] Dae-Jin Kim, Amanda R Bolbecker, Josselyn Howell, Olga Rass, Olaf Sporns, William P Hetrick, Alan Breier, Brian F O'Donnell, Disturbed resting state EEG synchronization in bipolar disorder: A graph-theoretic analysis, *Neuroimage Clin.* 22 (2013) 414–423, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2013.03.007>, (ISSN: 2213-1582 (Print); 2213-1582 (Electronic); 2213-1582 (Linking)).
- [35] Baris Metin, Çağlar Uyulan, Turker Tekin Erguzel, Shams Farhad, Elvan Cifci, Omer Turk, Nevzat Tarhan, The deep learning method differentiates patients with bipolar disorder from controls with high accuracy using EEG data, *Clin. EEG Neurosci.* (2022) 15500594221137234, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/15500594221137234>, (ISSN: 2169-5202 (Electronic); 1550-0594 (Linking)).
- [36] Raffaele Ferri, Francesco Rundo, Oliviero Bruni, Mario G Terzano, Cornelis J Stam, Small-world network organization of functional connectivity of EEG slow-wave activity during sleep, *J. Clin. Neurophysiol.* 118 (2) (2007) 449–456, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2006.10.021>, (ISSN: 1388-2457 (Print); 1388-2457 (Linking)).
- [37] Haoqi Sun, Wolfgang Ganglberger, Ezhil Panneerselvam, Michael J Leone, Syed A Quadri, Balaji Goparaju, Ryan A Tesh, Oluwaseun Akeju, Robert J Thomas, M Brandon Westover, Sleep staging from electrocardiography and respiration with deep learning, *Sleep* 43 (7) (2020) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/sleep/zsz306>, (ISSN: 1550-9109 (Electronic); 0161-8105 (Print); 0161-8105 (Linking)).
- [38] Piotr Mirowski, Deepak Madhavan, Yann LeCun, Ruben Kuzniecky, Classification of patterns of EEG synchronization for seizure prediction, *J. Clin. Neurophysiol.* 120 (11) (2009) 1927–1940, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2009.09.002>, (ISSN: 1872-8952 (Electronic); 1388-2457 (Linking)).
- [39] Luiz A. Bacalá, Milkes Y. Alvarenga, Koichi Sameshima, Carmen L Jorge, Luiz H Castro, Graph theoretical characterization and tracking of the effective neural connectivity during episodes of mesial temporal epileptic seizure, *J. Integr. Neurosci.* 3 (4) (2004) 379–395, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1142/s0219635204000610>, (ISSN: 0219-6352 (Print); 0219-6352 (Linking)).
- [40] Michael G Hart, Rolf J F Ypma, Rafael Romero-Garcia, Stephen J Price, John Suckling, Graph theory analysis of complex brain networks: new concepts in brain mapping applied to neurosurgery, *J. Neurosurg.* 124 (6) (2016) 1665–1678, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3171/2015.4.JNS142683>, (ISSN: 1933-0693 (Electronic); 0022-3085 (Linking)).
- [41] J Hammer, R T Schirmer, K Hartmann, P Marusic, A Schulze-Bonhage, T Ball, Interpretable functional specialization emerges in deep convolutional networks trained on brain signals, *J. Neural Eng.* 19 (3) (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ac6770>, (ISSN: 1741-2552 (Electronic); 1741-2552 (Linking)).
- [42] Yannick Roy, Hubert Banville, Isabela Albuquerque, Alexandre Gramfort, Tiago H Falk, Jocelyn Faubert, Deep learning-based electroencephalography analysis: a systematic review, *J. Neural Eng.* 16 (5) (2019) 051001, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ab260c>, (ISSN: 1741-2552 (Electronic); 1741-2552 (Linking)).
- [43] Maham Saeidi, Waldemar Karwowski, Farzad V Farahani, Krzysztof Fiok, Redha Taiar, P A Hancock, Awad Al-Juaid, Neural decoding of EEG signals with machine learning: A systematic review, *Brain Sci.* 11 (11) (2021) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11111525>, (ISSN: 2076-3425 (Print); 2076-3425 (Electronic); 2076-3425 (Linking)).
- [44] Fernando Andreotti, Huy Phan, Navin Cooray, Christine Lo, Michele T M Hu, Maarten De Vos, Multichannel sleep stage classification and transfer learning using convolutional neural networks, *Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc.* 2018 (2018) 171–174, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/EMBC.2018.8512214>, (ISSN: 2694-0604 (Electronic); 2375-7477 (Linking)).
- [45] Xuyun Sun, Cunle Qian, Zhongqin Chen, Zhaohui Wu, Benyan Luo, Gang Pan, Remembered or forgotten?—an EEG-based computational prediction approach, *PLoS One* 11 (12) (2016) e0167497, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0167497>, (ISSN: 1932-6203 (Electronic); 1932-6203 (Linking)).
- [46] U Rajendra Acharya, Shu Lih Oh, Yuki Hagiwara, Jen Hong Tan, Hojjat Adeli, D P Subha, Automated EEG-based screening of depression using deep convolutional neural network, *Comput. Methods Prog. Biomed.* 161 (2018) 103–113, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2018.04.012>, (ISSN: 1872-7565 (Electronic); 0169-2607 (Linking)).
- [47] Nibras Abo Alzahab, Luca Apollonio, Angelo Di Iorio, Muaaz Alshalak, Sabrina Iarlori, Francesco Ferracuti, Andrea Monteriù, Camillo Porcaro, Hybrid deep learning (hDL)-based brain-computer interface (BCI) systems: A systematic review, *Brain Sci.* 11 (1) (2021) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/brainsci11010075>, (ISSN: 2076-3425 (Print); 2076-3425 (Electronic); 2076-3425 (Linking)).
- [48] Muhammad Najam Dar, Muhammad Usman Akram, Sajid Gul Khawaja, Amit N Pujari, CNN and LSTM-based emotion charting using physiological signals, *Sensors (Basel)* 20 (16) (2020) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/s20164551>, (ISSN: 1424-8220 (Electronic); 1424-8220 (Linking)).
- [49] Zied Tayeb, Juri Fedjaev, Nejla Ghaboosi, Christoph Richter, Lukas Everding, Xingwei Qu, Yingyu Wu, Gordon Cheng, Jörg Conradt, Validating deep neural networks for online decoding of motor imagery movements from EEG signals, *Sensors (Basel)* 19 (1) (2019) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/s19010210>, (ISSN: 1424-8220 (Electronic); 1424-8220 (Linking)).
- [50] Fengjie Wu, Weijian Mai, Yisheng Tang, Qingkun Liu, Jiangtao Chen, Ziqian Guo, Learning spatial-spectral-temporal EEG representations with deep attentive-recurrent-convolutional neural networks for pain intensity assessment, *Neuroscience* 481 (2022) 144–155, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroscience.2021.11.034>, (ISSN: 1873-7544 (Electronic); 0306-4522 (Linking)).
- [51] Chih-En Kuo, Tsung-Hua Lu, Guan-Ting Chen, Po-Yu Liao, Towards precision sleep medicine: Self-attention GAN as an innovative data augmentation technique for developing personalized automatic sleep scoring classification, *Comput. Biol. Med.* 148 (2022) 105828, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.combiomed.2022.105828>, (ISSN: 1879-0534 (Electronic); 0010-4825 (Linking)).
- [52] Sajad Mousavi, Fatemeh Afghah, U. Rajendra Acharya, SleepEEGNet: Automated sleep stage scoring with sequence to sequence deep learning approach, *PLoS One* 14 (5) (2019) e0216456, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0216456>, (ISSN: 1932-6203 (Electronic); 1932-6203 (Linking)).
- [53] A. Sperduti, A. Starita, Supervised neural networks for the classification of structures, *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw.* 8 (3) (1997) 714–735, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/72.572108>, (ISSN: 1045-9227 (Print); 1045-9227 (Linking)).
- [54] Claudio Gallicchio, Alessio Micheli, Graph echo state networks, in: *The 2010 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, 2010, pp. 1–8, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN.2010.5596796>.
- [55] M. Gori, G. Monfardini, F. Scarselli, A new model for learning in graph domains, in: *Proceedings. 2005 IEEE International Joint Conference on Neural Networks, 2005*, Vol. 2, 2005, pp. 729–734, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN.2005.1555942>, vol. 2.
- [56] Franco Scarselli, Marco Gori, Ah Chung Tsoi, Markus Hagenbuchner, Gabriele Monfardini, The graph neural network model, *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw.* 20 (1) (2009) 61–80, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNN.2008.2005605>.
- [57] Mathias Niepert, Mohamed Ahmed, Konstantin Kutuzov, Learning convolutional neural networks for graphs, in: *Maria Florina Balcan, Kilian Q. Weinberger (Eds.), Proceedings of the 33rd International Conference on Machine Learning*, in: *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 48, PMLR, New York, New York, USA, 2016, pp. 2014–2023, URL <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v48/niepert16.html>.
- [58] Bing Yu, Haoteng Yin, Zhanxing Zhu, Spatio-temporal graph convolutional networks: A deep learning framework for traffic forecasting, in: *Proceedings of the Twenty-Seventh International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence Organization, 2018*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2018/505>.
- [59] Joan Bruna, Wojciech Zaremba, Arthur Szlam, Yann LeCun, Spectral networks and locally connected networks on graphs, 2013, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1312.6203>, URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1312.6203>.
- [60] Michael Defferrard, Xavier Bresson, Pierre Vandergheynst, Convolutional neural networks on graphs with fast localized spectral filtering, 2016, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1606.09375>, URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1606.09375>.
- [61] Mikael Henaff, Joan Bruna, Yann LeCun, Deep convolutional networks on graph-structured data, 2015, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1506.05163>, URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1506.05163>.
- [62] Thomas N. Kipf, Max Welling, Semi-supervised classification with graph convolutional networks, 2016, <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1609.02907>, URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/1609.02907>.
- [63] Ron Levie, Federico Monti, Xavier Bresson, Michael M. Bronstein, CayleyNets: Graph convolutional neural networks with complex rational spectral filters, *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.* 67 (1) (2019) 97–109, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TSP.2018.2879624>.
- [64] David I Shuman, Sunil K. Narang, Pascal Frossard, Antonio Ortega, Pierre Vandergheynst, The emerging field of signal processing on graphs: Extending high-dimensional data analysis to networks and other irregular domains, *IEEE Signal Process. Mag.* 30 (3) (2013) 83–98, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MSP.2012.2235192>.
- [65] David K. Hammond, Pierre Vandergheynst, Rémi Gribonval, Wavelets on graphs via spectral graph theory, *Appl. Comput. Harmon. Anal.* (ISSN: 1063-5203) 30 (2) (2011) 129–150, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.acha.2010.04.005>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1063520310000552>.
- [66] Naishi Feng, Fo Hu, Hong Wang, Bin Zhou, Motor intention decoding from the upper limb by graph convolutional network based on functional connectivity, *Int. J. Neural Syst.* 31 (12) (2021) 2150047, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1142/S0129065721500477>, (ISSN: 1793-6462 (Electronic); 0129-0657 (Linking)).
- [67] Xiaowei Che, Yuanjie Zheng, Xin Chen, Sutao Song, Shouxin Li, Decoding color visual working memory from EEG signals using graph convolutional neural networks, *Int. J. Neural Syst.* 32 (2) (2022) 2250003, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1142/S0129065722500034>, (ISSN: 1793-6462 (Electronic); 0129-0657 (Linking)).

- [68] Yimin Hou, Shuyue Jia, Xiangmin Lun, Ziqian Hao, Yan Shi, Yang Li, Rui Zeng, Jinglei Lv, GCNs-net: A graph convolutional neural network approach for decoding time-resolved EEG motor imagery signals, *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw. Learn. Syst.* PP (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNNLS.2022.3202569>, (ISSN: 2162-2388 (Electronic); 2162-237X (Linking)).
- [69] Andac Demir, Toshiaki Koike-Akino, Ye Wang, Masaki Haruna, Deniz Erdogmus, EEG-GNN: Graph neural networks for classification of electroencephalogram (EEG) signals, *Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc.* 2021 (2021) 1061–1067, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/EMBC46164.2021.9630194>, (ISSN: 2694-0604 (Electronic); 2375-7477 (Linking)).
- [70] Yan Li, Ning Zhong, David Taniar, Haolan Zhang, MCGNet(+): an improved motor imagery classification based on cosine similarity, *Brain Inform.* 9 (1) (2022) 3, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40708-021-00151-3>, (ISSN: 2198-4018 (Print); 2198-4026 (Electronic); 2198-4026 (Linking)).
- [71] Yimin Hou, Shuyue Jia, Xiangmin Lun, Shu Zhang, Tao Chen, Fang Wang, Jinglei Lv, Deep feature mining via the attention-based bidirectional long short term memory graph convolutional neural network for human motor imagery recognition, *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 9 (2021) 706229, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2021.706229>, (ISSN: 2296-4185 (Print); 2296-4185 (Electronic); 2296-4185 (Linking)).
- [72] Zhichuan Tang, Lingtao Zhang, Xin Chen, Jichen Ying, Xinyang Wang, Hang Wang, Wearable supernumerary robotic limb system using a hybrid control approach based on motor imagery and object detection, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* 30 (2022) 1298–1309, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2022.3172974>, (ISSN: 1558-0210 (Electronic); 1534-4320 (Linking)).
- [73] Runnan Lu, Ying Zeng, Rongkai Zhang, Bin Yan, Li Tong, SAST-GCN: Segmentation adaptive spatial temporal-graph convolutional network for P3-based video target detection, *Front. Neurosci.* 16 (2022) 913027, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2022.913027>, (ISSN: 1662-4548 (Print); 1662-453X (Electronic); 1662-453X (Linking)).
- [74] Lili Shen, Mingyang Sun, Qunxia Li, Beichen Li, Zhaoqing Pan, Jianjun Lei, Multiscale temporal self-attention and dynamical graph convolution hybrid network for EEG-based stereogram recognition, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* 30 (2022) 1191–1202, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2022.3173724>, (ISSN: 1558-0210 (Electronic); 1534-4320 (Linking)).
- [75] Weiwei Zhang, Fei Wang, Shichao Wu, Zongfeng Xu, Jingyu Ping, Yang Jiang, Partial directed coherence based graph convolutional neural networks for driving fatigue detection, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.* 91 (7) (2020) 074713, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/5.0008434>.
- [76] Andac Demir, Toshiaki Koike-Akino, Ye Wang, Deniz Erdogmus, EEG-GAT: Graph attention networks for classification of electroencephalogram (EEG) signals, *Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc.* 2022 (2022) 30–35, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/EMBC48229.2022.9871984>, (ISSN: 2694-0604 (Electronic); 2375-7477 (Linking)).
- [77] Ziyu Jia, Youfang Lin, Jing Wang, Xiaojun Ning, Yuanlai He, Ronghao Zhou, Yuhang Zhou, Li-Wei H Lehman, Multi-view spatial-temporal graph convolutional networks with domain generalization for sleep stage classification, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* 29 (2021) 1977–1986, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2021.3110665>, (ISSN: 1558-0210 (Electronic); 1534-4320 (Print); 1534-4320 (Linking)).
- [78] Xiaopeng Ji, Yan Li, Peng Wen, Jumping knowledge based spatial-temporal graph convolutional networks for automatic sleep stage classification, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* 30 (2022) 1464–1472, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2022.3176004>, (ISSN: 1558-0210 (Electronic); 1534-4320 (Linking)).
- [79] Menglei Li, Hongbo Chen, Zixue Cheng, An attention-guided spatiotemporal graph convolutional network for sleep stage classification, *Life (Basel)* 12 (5) (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/life12050622>, (ISSN: 2075-1729 (Print); 2075-1729 (Electronic); 2075-1729 (Linking)).
- [80] Qi Lian, Yu Qi, Gang Pan, Yueming Wang, Learning graph in graph convolutional neural networks for robust seizure prediction, *J. Neural Eng.* 17 (3) (2020) 035004, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ab909d>, (ISSN: 1741-2552 (Electronic); 1741-2552 (Linking)).
- [81] Manhua Jia, Wenjian Liu, Junwei Duan, Long Chen, C L Philip Chen, Qun Wang, Zhiguo Zhou, Efficient graph convolutional networks for seizure prediction using scalp EEG, *Front. Neurosci.* 16 (2022) 967116, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2022.967116>, (ISSN: 1662-4548 (Print); 1662-453X (Electronic); 1662-453X (Linking)).
- [82] Jian Lian, Fangzhou Xu, Spatial enhanced pattern through graph convolutional neural network for epileptic EEG identification, *Int. J. Neural Syst.* 32 (9) (2022) 2250033, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1142/S0129065722500332>, (ISSN: 1793-6462 (Electronic); 0129-0657 (Linking)).
- [83] Yang Li, Yu Liu, Yu-Zhu Guo, Xiao-Feng Liao, Bin Hu, Tao Yu, Spatio-temporal-spectral hierarchical graph convolutional network with semisupervised active learning for patient-specific seizure prediction, *IEEE Trans. Cybern.* 52 (11) (2022) 12189–12204, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TCYB.2021.3071860>, (ISSN: 2168-2275 (Electronic); 2168-2267 (Linking)).
- [84] Yanna Zhao, Changxu Dong, Gaobo Zhang, Yaru Wang, Xin Chen, Weikuan Jia, Qi Yuan, Fangzhou Xu, Yuanjie Zheng, EEG-based seizure detection using linear graph convolution network with focal loss., *Comput. Methods Prog. Biomed.* 208 (2021) 106277, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2021.106277>, (ISSN: 1872-7565 (Electronic); 0169-2607 (Linking)).
- [85] Zhengdao Li, Kai Hwang, Keqin Li, Jie Wu, Tongkai Ji, Graph-generative neural network for EEG-based epileptic seizure detection via discovery of dynamic brain functional connectivity, *Sci. Rep.* 12 (1) (2022) 18998, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-23656-1>,
- [86] Shiva Asadzadeh, Tohid Yousefi Rezaii, Soosan Beheshti, Saeed Meshgini, Accurate emotion recognition using Bayesian model based EEG sources as dynamic graph convolutional neural network nodes, *Sci. Rep.* 12 (1) (2022) 10282, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-14217-7>, (ISSN: 2045-2322 (Electronic); 2045-2322 (Linking)).
- [87] Ming Jin, Hao Chen, Zhunan Li, Jinpeng Li, EEG-based emotion recognition using graph convolutional network with learnable electrode relations, *Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc.* 2021 (2021) 5953–5957, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/EMBC46164.2021.9630195>, (ISSN: 2694-0604 (Electronic); 2375-7477 (Linking)).
- [88] Guangqiang Li, Ning Chen, Jing Jin, Semi-supervised EEG emotion recognition model based on enhanced graph fusion and GCN, *J. Neural Eng.* 19 (2) (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ac63ec>, (ISSN: 1741-2552 (Electronic); 1741-2552 (Linking)).
- [89] Jingcong Li, Shuqi Li, Jiahui Pan, Fei Wang, Cross-subject EEG emotion recognition with self-organized graph neural network, *Front. Neurosci.* 15 (2021) 611653, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2021.611653>, (ISSN: 1662-4548 (Print); 1662-453X (Electronic); 1662-453X (Linking)).
- [90] Shuai Luo, Yu-Ting Lan, Dan Peng, Ziyi Li, Wei-Long Zheng, Bao-Liang Lu, Multimodal emotion recognition in response to oil paintings, *Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc.* 2022 (2022) 4167–4170, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/EMBC48229.2022.9871630>, (ISSN: 2694-0604 (Electronic); 2375-7477 (Linking)).
- [91] Jing Zhang, Xueying Zhang, Guijun Chen, Qing Zhao, Granger-causality-based multi-frequency band EEG graph feature extraction and fusion for emotion recognition, *Brain Sci.* 12 (12) (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12121649>.
- [92] Huijuan Zhao, Jingjin Liu, Zhenqian Shen, Jingwen Yan, SCC-MPGCN: self-attention coherence clustering based on multi-pooling graph convolutional network for EEG emotion recognition, *J. Neural Eng.* 19 (2) (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/ac6294>.
- [93] Guangcheng Bao, Kai Yang, Li Tong, Jun Shu, Rongkai Zhang, Linyuan Wang, Bin Yan, Ying Zeng, Linking multi-layer dynamical GCN with style-based recalibration CNN for EEG-based emotion recognition, *Front. Neurosci.* 16 (2022) 834952, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fnbot.2022.834952>, (ISSN: 1662-5218 (Print); 1662-5218 (Electronic); 1662-5218 (Linking)).
- [94] Yalan Ye, Xin Zhu, Yunxia Li, Tongjie Pan, Wenwen He, Cross-subject EEG-based emotion recognition using adversarial domain adaption with attention mechanism, *Annu. Int. Conf. IEEE Eng. Med. Biol. Soc.* 2021 (2021) 1140–1144, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/EMBC46164.2021.9630777>, (ISSN: 2694-0604 (Electronic); 2375-7477 (Linking)).
- [95] Wenli Tian, Ming Li, Xiangyu Ju, Yadong Liu, Applying multiple functional connectivity features in GCN for EEG-based human identification, *Brain Sci.* 12 (8) (2022) <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12081072>, (ISSN: 2076-3425 (Print); 2076-3425 (Electronic); 2076-3425 (Linking)).
- [96] Xiaocai Shan, Jun Cao, Shoudong Huo, Liangyu Chen, Ptolemaios Georgios Sarrigiannis, Yifan Zhao, Spatial-temporal graph convolutional network for Alzheimer classification based on brain functional connectivity imaging of electroencephalogram., *Hum. Brain Mapp.* 43 (17) (2022) 5194–5209, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/hbm.25994>, (ISSN: 1097-0193 (Electronic); 1065-9471 (Print); 1065-9471 (Linking)).
- [97] Qi Chang, Cancheng Li, Qing Tian, Qijing Bo, Jicong Zhang, Yanbing Xiong, Chuanyue Wang, Classification of first-episode schizophrenia, chronic schizophrenia and healthy control based on brain network of mismatch negativity by graph neural network, *IEEE Trans. Neural Syst. Rehabil. Eng.* 29 (2021) 1784–1794, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TNSRE.2021.3105669>, (ISSN: 1558-0210 (Electronic); 1534-4320 (Linking)).
- [98] Taban Fami Tafreshi, Mohammad Reza Daliri, Mahrad Ghodousi, Functional and effective connectivity based features of EEG signals for object recognition, *Cognit. Neurodyn.* 13 (6) (2019) 555–566, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11571-019-09556-7>, (ISSN: 1871-4080 (Print); 1871-4099 (Electronic); 1871-4080 (Linking)).
- [99] Pieter van Mierlo, Margarita Papadopoulou, Evelien Carrette, Paul Boon, Stefaan Vandenbergh, Kristl Vonck, Daniele Marinazzo, Functional brain connectivity from EEG in epilepsy: seizure prediction and epileptogenic focus localization, *Prog. Neurobiol.* 121 (2014) 19–35, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.pneurobio.2014.06.004>, (ISSN: 1873-5118 (Electronic); 0301-0082 (Linking)).
- [100] C.J. Stam, B.W. van Dijk, Synchronization likelihood: an unbiased measure of generalized synchronization in multivariate data sets, *Physica D* (ISSN: 0167-2789) 163 (3) (2002) 236–251, [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2789\(01\)00386-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0167-2789(01)00386-4), URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167278901003864>.

- [101] Troy M. Lau, Joseph T. Gwin, Kaleb G. McDowell, Daniel P. Ferris, Weighted phase lag index stability as an artifact resistant measure to detect cognitive EEG activity during locomotion, *J. NeuroEng. Rehabil.* 9 (1) (2012) 47, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1743-0003-9-47>,
- [102] R.G. Stockwell, L. Mansinha, R.P. Lowe, Localization of the complex spectrum: The s transform, *IEEE Trans. Signal Process.* 44 (4) (1996) 998–1001, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/78.492555>, URL <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-0030127735&doi=10.1109%2f78.492555&partnerID=40&md5=3e59d5100ab7715eb0bd4660f5b51acc>. Cited by: 2527.
- [103] Pamela D Butler, Yue Chen, Judith M Ford, Mark A Geyer, Steven M Silverstein, Michael F Green, Perceptual measurement in schizophrenia: promising electrophysiology and neuroimaging paradigms from CNTRICS, *Schizophr. Bull.* 38 (1) (2012) 81–91, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/schbul/sbr106>, (ISSN: 1745-1701 (Electronic); 0586-7614 (Print); 0586-7614 (Linking)).
- [104] Dean F Salisbury, Nicola R Polizzotto, Paul G Nestor, Sarah M Haigh, Justine Koehler, Robert W McCarley, Pitch and duration mismatch negativity and premorbid intellect in the first hospitalized schizophrenia spectrum, *Schizophr. Bull.* 43 (2) (2017) 407–416, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/schbul/sbw074>, (ISSN: 1745-1701 (Electronic); 0586-7614 (Print); 0586-7614 (Linking)).
- [105] Sou Nobukawa, Teruya Yamanishi, Shinya Kasakawa, Haruhiko Nishimura, Mitsuru Kikuchi, Tetsuya Takahashi, Classification methods based on complexity and synchronization of electroencephalography signals in Alzheimer's disease, *Front. Psychiatry* 11 (2020) 255, <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.00255>, (ISSN: 1664-0640 (Print); 1664-0640 (Electronic); 1664-0640 (Linking)).